

FEATURES OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE ANATOMICAL LUNG RESECTION
REPUBLICAN SPECIALIZED SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL MEDICAL CENTER OF
SURGERY

named after Academician
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Abstract. This article presents the results of surgical treatment of 13 patients who underwent minimally invasive anatomical lung resections using video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery (VATS) between 2023 and 2025.

Aim: To evaluate the clinical, intraoperative and early postoperative outcomes of VATS lobectomy in patients with various lung diseases.

Materials and methods: A retrospective analysis of surgical treatment outcomes was performed in 13 patients treated at the Department of Thoracic Surgery of the State Institution “Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Surgery named after Academician V. Vakhidov” between 2023 and 2025. The patients’ age ranged from 23 to 75 years. All patients underwent anatomical lung resections using a video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery (VATS) approach.

Results: The duration of the operation was 286 ± 109 minutes. The length of hospital stay ranged from 5 to 18 days. Complications were observed in 1 patient (7.7%). In the majority of cases, the postoperative period was uneventful.

Conclusion: Thus, the obtained results indicate the safety and clinical efficacy of video-assisted thoracoscopic anatomical lung resections in a carefully selected group of patients.

Keywords: Video-assisted thoracoscopy, anatomical lung resection, VATS, lobectomy, minimally invasive surgery.

Introduction.

In recent years, significant progress has been observed in the development of minimally invasive thoracic surgery [2,3]. Video-assisted thoracic surgery (VATS) has gradually become the “gold standard” in the treatment of pulmonary diseases, including benign and malignant lung lesions [7,8].

Anatomical lung resections (segmentectomy and lobectomy) are considered the main radical methods of surgical treatment [1]. The implementation of these procedures through minimally invasive access has become a major breakthrough in thoracic surgery [7,9]. In Uzbekistan, this field continues to develop actively; however, systematic studies reflecting the experience of domestic clinics remain insufficient [4]. Over the past three decades since the introduction of the first VATS procedures, these operations have been widely adopted in many medical institutions [7,8].

Continuous improvement of surgical instruments contributes to the expansion of VATS applications in thoracic surgery and reduces the number of absolute contraindications for minimally invasive procedures [2,3].

Since its emergence at the beginning of the last century, minimally invasive thoracic surgery has undergone a long period of development. Many authors have reported significant advantages of VATS compared to open surgery, including reduced surgical trauma, lower postoperative pain, shorter hospital stay, and faster postoperative rehabilitation [5,7,8].

Video-assisted thoracoscopy is widely used not only for therapeutic purposes but also for the differential diagnosis of intrathoracic neoplasms and peripheral pulmonary lesions [1-3].

Modern international studies demonstrate the high efficacy and safety of VATS lobectomy in patients with various lung diseases [6-10].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, minimally invasive technologies in thoracic surgery continue to be actively introduced into clinical practice; however, the number of domestic studies dedicated to the analysis of VATS anatomical lung resections remains limited [4].

Materials and methods. A retrospective analysis was conducted of the outcomes of surgical treatment in 13 patients at the Department of Thoracic Surgery of the State Institution ‘V. Vakhidov Research Centre for Thoracic Surgery’ between 2023 and 2025. The mean age ranged from 23 to 75 years (tab.2), all patients underwent anatomical lung resections using the video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery (VATS) technique. The main indications for surgical intervention were peripheral and central lung tumours, adenocarcinoma, carcinoid tumours, metastatic lesions and residual cavities. The duration of the operation, length of hospital stay and frequency of postoperative complications were assessed. Surgeries were performed under general anaesthesia with separate bronchial intubation and one-lung ventilation.

Video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery was performed using the standard three-port technique. Following mobilisation of the vascular structures and the bronchus, anatomical resection was performed using endoscopic staplers.

Results. The duration of the operation was 286 ± 109 minutes. The increased duration of the operation was attributed to the learning curve associated with the video-assisted thoracoscopic technique, significant adhesions in a number of patients, and the technical challenges involved in dissecting the vascular-bronchial structures. No cases of massive intraoperative blood loss or fatalities were observed. Conversion to open thoracotomy was not required. The length of hospital stay ranged from 5 to 18 days.

Longer hospitalisation was observed in patients with comorbidities and marked post-inflammatory changes in lung tissue. Postoperative complications were observed in 1 patient (7.7%). In the majority of cases, the postoperative period was uneventful. The results obtained demonstrate the feasibility of safely performing anatomical lung resections using video-assisted thoracoscopic access with appropriate patient selection.

Conclusion. Anatomical lung resections performed using video-assisted thoracic surgery are an effective and safe method for the surgical treatment of patients with various lung diseases. The use of VATS technologies reduces surgical trauma, decreases the incidence of postoperative complications, and provides a favorable postoperative course. The obtained results confirm the prospects for further implementation of minimally invasive technologies in thoracic surgical practice.

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